

REDUCTION OF THE NEGATIVE IMPACT OF VEHICLE TRANSPORT ON THE ENVIRONMENT, POPULATION AND WORKERS

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Annotation. When burning any fuel, various combustion emissions are released. These wastes have a great impact on human health and the environment. Factories, factories and motor transport enterprises in the city are the main sources of environmental pollution. If the plants and factories are located in one specific place and pollute this place, and cars will have an effect wherever they work. Motor transport is currently considered to be more polluting of the environment than factories and plants. In this article, the composition of exhaust gases emitted by motor vehicles during operation, their harmful effects on the environment and ways to eliminate them, environmental and environmental damage are described in this article. factors, their legal prevention and solution, as well as conclusions and suggestions for the above problems.

Keywords: automobile, toxic gases, carbon dioxide, nitrogen oxides, exhaust gases.

Enter: The biggest problem at the moment is to reduce the toxic emissions from the use of cars.

Today there are 500 million cars on the world's roads, and by 2030 their number is expected to reach 1 billion. According to economists, after 22 years, the number of car owners will double. According to estimates, 1 passenger car emits up to 1 kilogram of exhaust gases into the air during the day.

The main source of exhaust gases (or used gases) is the internal combustion engine - these are substances with different chemical and physical properties in the

form of inhomogeneous gas as a result of full or partial combustion of fuel, air, aerosols and various micromixtures, which fall from the engine cylinder into the exhaust system. It was found that the main harmful emissions emitted by the car, currently there are more than 200 toxic emissions in the gas produced by fuel combustion. The most toxic include: carbon monoxide-CO, unburned hydrocarbons-CN, nitrogen oxides - NO_x[1].

Many countries have introduced regulations for these wastes. The regulation of emissions from fuel combustion in our country was introduced in 1970 based on the instructions issued by the European Economic Commission of the UN. (EEKOON).

The exhaust gases of engines running on ethylated gasoline contain lead, and engines running on diesel fuel contain more soot. Carbon monoxide (SO-is gas). Transparent, odorless, toxic, light compared to air, poorly soluble in water.

Carbon monoxide is a byproduct of incomplete combustion of fuel and burns with a bluish flame as carbon dioxide forms in the air. In the engine combustion chamber, SO is formed as a result of insufficient fuel injection, cold flame reaction, combustion of fuel with insufficient oxygen and dissociation of carbon dioxide at high temperatures. During post-ignition combustion (after the high end point, during the expansion stroke), carbon monoxide is burned by mixing with oxygen when dioxide is formed. In this case, SO combustion continues in the outlet pipeline. It should also be taken into account that when operating diesel engines, the amount of SO in exhaust gases is small (about 0.1-0.2 percent), so the amount of SO is determined only for gasoline engines. Nitrogen oxides (NO, NO₂, N₂O, N₂O₃, N₂O₅, later - NO_x). Nitrous oxide is one of the most toxic components of car exhaust. Under normal atmospheric conditions, nitrogen is like an inert gas. At high pressure and high temperature, nitrogen actively reacts with oxygen. 90 percent of NO_x in engine exhaust gases is nitrogen xide NO, which is then oxidized to nitrogen dioxide NO₂ in the exhaust system[2].

The approximate composition of gases coming out of nuclear reactors is presented in Table 1.

Composition of exhaust gases

Table 1.

Waste gases component	Amount by size, %		Explanation
	Engines		
	gasoline	diesel	
Carbon monoxide	0,1 - 10,0	0,01 - 5,0	poisonous
Aldehydes	0-0,2	0,001 - 0,009	poisonous
Non-toxic hydrocarbons	0,2 - 3,0	0,009 - 0,5	poisonous
Sulfur oxide	0 - 0,002	0 - 0,03	poisonous
Benzopyrene, mg/m ³	0,01 - 0,02	Do 0,01	poisonous
Alighting, g/m ³	0 - 0,04	0,01 - 1,1	poisonous

Nitric oxide NO affects the tear film of the eye and damages the human lungs because it interacts with moisture in the upper respiratory tract as it moves through the respiratory tract to form nitric and nitrous acids. Usually, NOx poisoning of a person's organism does not happen at once, it happens gradually, there are no means to neutralize them. Nitrous oxide (N₂O-hemioxide, happy gas) is an odorous gas that dissolves well in water. It has a narcotic effect. NO₂ (dioxide)-leaking is involved in the formation of yellow liquid, smoky haze. When the concentration of nitrogen oxide in the air is 0.5-6.0 mg/m³, it has a direct toxic effect on trees. Nitric acid causes severe corrosion of carbon steels.

Hydrocarbons (C_nH_m-ethane, methane, ethylene, benzene, propane, acetylene, etc.). Hydrocarbons are organic compounds whose molecules consist only of carbon and hydrogen atoms and are toxic substances. Waste gases contain more than 200 different hydrocarbons, divided into aliphatic and aromatic rings. In an aromatic hydrocarbon molecule, one or more rings consist of 6 carbon atoms and are interconnected by simple or double bonds. It has a fragrant smell. The

mixture in the combustion chamber is not homogeneous due to the presence of SN content in the used gases of the engine, therefore, the flame extinguishing occurs on the walls of the cylinder where the fuel mixture is located, and this is explained by the interruption of the chain reaction. (Figure 1)

Figure 1. Exhaust gas system diagram 1 - exhaust valve; 2 — exhaust pipeline; 3 — exhaust pipe of the muffler; 4 — additional muffler (resonator); 5 — main muffler; 6 — connecting clamps

Incompletely burned SN, leaving with waste gases, contains several hundreds of chemical compounds, has an unpleasant smell, and is the cause of many chronic diseases. Gasoline fumes are also toxic because they are also hydrocarbons. The average daily concentration of gasoline vapors is 1.5 mg/m³. SN in the exhaust gases increases during throttling and forced idle mode. In the above operating mode of the engine, the process of mixture formation is disturbed, the combustion speed decreases, the ignition deteriorates, as a result of which more exhaust is released. Hydrocarbons appear in the rich mixture regions of the cylinder, in the oxygen-poor and relatively cold walls. They actively participate in the formation of biologically active substances, which irritate the eyes and nose and cause them to become sick. In addition, hydrocarbons cause great harm to flora and fauna. Hydrocarbon compounds have a narcotic effect on the central nervous system, can cause chronic diseases, some SNs have toxic properties.

Hydrocarbons and nitrogen oxides create conditions for the formation of smoky fog (smog) in certain meteorological conditions.

Waste gases also contain harmless products: oxygen, carbon dioxide, nitrogen, sulfur. But nitrogen forms an oxide at high temperature and pressure, which is extremely toxic. According to many sources, toxic products in waste gases are not always in the same volume. It depends on the type of engines, operating mode, how they are tuned, engine maintenance and fuel quality[3].

Figure 2. Toxic emissions released during the operation of the car.

Effects of waste gases on the environment and people

Exhaust gas is a work product developed in the engine. It is an incompletely burned hydrocarbon fuel and an oxidation product. The emission of waste gases causes an increase in the permissible concentration of toxic substances and carcinogens in the atmosphere of cities. The formation of smog can be the cause of poisoning in a closed environment.

Figure 3. Smoke from cars in traffic jams

The amount of exhaust gases emitted by cars The amount of gases emitted by cars is determined by the amount of fuel consumption. Fuel consumption is measured against the distance traveled and specified by the car manufacturer. Estimated fuel consumption can be determined depending on the volume of exhaust gases coming out of the car's tailpipe. When one kg of gasoline burns, 16 kg of different gas mixtures are produced.[4,5]

- k — carburetor engine
- i — injection engine
- D — diesel engine
- gasoline +20S density from 0.69 to 0.81 g/cm³
- density of diesel fuel not more than 0.86 g/cm³ at +20C according to GOST 305-82.

The composition of car exhaust gases

Table 2.

	Gasoline	Diesel
N ₂ , ob. %	74- 77	76-78
O ₂ , ob. %	0,3- 8,0	2,0 - 18,0
H ₂ O (steam), ob. %	3,0- 5,5	0,5 - 4,0
CO ₂ , ob. %	0,0 -16,0	1,0 - 10,0

CO*, ob. %	0,1- 5,0	0,01 - 0,5
Nitrous oxide *, ob. %	0,0- 0,8	0,0002 - 0,5
Hydrocarbons *, ob. %	0,2- 3,0	0,09 - 0,5
Aldehydes*, ob. %	0,0 - 0,2	0,001-0,009
Saja**, g/m ³	0,0 - 0,4	0,01-1,10
Benzpyrene -3,4**, g/m ³	10 - 20·10 ⁻⁶	10*10 ⁻⁶

Toxic components

Carcinogens

Ways to reduce toxic waste

To reduce the toxicity of waste gases, work is being carried out in 2 different directions:

I - Improvement of the engine operation mode, use of various auxiliary equipment and high-quality fuel, adjustment works.

Incentives to reduce toxic emissions are primarily incentives to reduce fuel consumption. The amount of waste (excluding fuel consumption and time) is greatly influenced by the organization of traffic in cities (most of the waste comes from traffic jams and traffic lights). When the movement is well organized, it is possible to use low-power engines at lower speeds.

- using passenger gases or natural gas as fuel can reduce hydrocarbons in exhaust gases by more than 2 times. The main disadvantage of natural gas is that it travels relatively less, which is not so important in urban conditions;

- In addition to the fuel composition, the condition and adjustment of the engine affects the toxicity of exhaust gases (mainly in diesel engines, the amount can increase up to 20 times, nitrogen oxide in the carburetor can increase up to 1.5-2 times);

- exhaust gases are reduced (reduced fuel consumption) in engines of modern design with injector supply system. In these engines, a constant

stoichiometric mixture of unleaded gasoline is created, a catalyst is installed, gas engine units are driven and air cooled, and mixed transmissions are used. But such structures make cars more expensive. SAE tests show that one of the ways to reduce nitrogen oxides in exhaust gases (up to 90%) and the total toxicity of gases is to spray water into the combustion chamber.

Finding a technical solution to environmental problems is carried out in three directions in world practice: the system of reducing the toxicity of fuel, engine and exhaust gases. Compulsory analysis of each of them is required, so we outline the task with several lines.

So, fuel. Meets fuel quality requirements. One of the ways to reduce the toxicity of used gases is to use compressed and liquefied gases as fuel. Almost 90% of gasoline engines in the Fergana Valley regions have been converted to gas cylinder cars, and more than 95% of gas cars are designed for methane gas.

The most promising is the use of hydrogen as a fuel. In this case, the engine's energetic and environmental performance will improve dramatically. The high heat of combustion of hydrogen is 120 MJ/kg and is much higher than the mass heat of other fuels: that of gasoline is 45 MJ/kg, and that of diesel fuel is 42.7 MJ/kg. However, due to the low density of hydrogen, its simple energy characteristics are low compared to petroleum fuels. The ability to release heat of the hydrogen-air mixture is 15 percent lower than the gasoline-air mixture 18 and 10 percent lower than the alcohol-air mixture.

Hydrogen is a promising type of fuel for engines, because it has an inexhaustible base of raw materials, a very high heat of combustion (its heat of combustion is 118045 kJ/kg), does not emit toxic substances (except nitrogen) during combustion, and does not deteriorate the properties of the oil. .

The high diffusion coefficient of hydrogen makes it possible to create a homogeneous mixture even when the fuel is transferred to the cylinder in any way, and to distribute it evenly to the cylinders in all operating modes of the engine. When hydrogen burns, it does not produce soot, soot and coke, which is optimal

from the point of view of corrosion of engine parts and service life. However, due to the low density of hydrogen, its volumetric energy capacity is relatively low. Combustion of a hydrogen fuel mixture is 6 times faster than the combustion rate of a gasoline-air mixture. A working mixture of hydrogen and air in a ratio of 1:10 is relatively effective. Hydrogen is characterized by a small lower flammability limit of the hydrogen mixture (the ratio of hydrogen and air is 1:25) and a very low ignition energy (12-14 times less than gasoline). These properties of hydrogen cause sparking in the pipes of the introduction of the working mixture, ignition of the working mixture in the cylinders before the specified time, the intensity of the combustion process, and detonation. As a result of these conditions, the work process in the carburettor engine is disturbed. In addition, the problem of storing and placing hydrogen in a car is one of the problems that need to be solved. For example, if the mass of the fuel tank is 13-15 kg to store the amount of fuel (gasoline or diesel fuel) sufficient to travel a certain reserve distance, the mass of the tank system for storing compressed hydrogen designed to travel the same distance 19 should be 1300-1400 kg. For these reasons, hydrogen is considered as a replacement material for petroleum-derived liquid fuels in the long term. Currently, work is underway to use hydrogen as an additive to reduce liquid fuel consumption.

II - Production of low-harmful engines: gas turbine, external combustion-Stirling engine, eletromobiles, etc.

A promising and effective strategic environmental initiative today is certainly engine design changes. The widespread use of injection engines, electronic control systems and the improvement of the working process of the engine have raised economy and environmental performance to a new level of quality. If we look at the concept of inventing an ecological engine, 30 years of research in world practice have only offered various forms, interesting projects and structures, but all of them have been turned into metal. An example of a rotor-piston engine can be given as an example, which differs from the classic IYOD in

terms of the toxicity of exhaust gases. Currently, these engines are produced at the Volzhsk plant only for installation on special equipment.

Currently, hybrid power units are used, which are the most efficient in terms of economy and environmental parameters: they work on highways with an internal combustion engine, and in urban areas they work with an electric motor. Switching to one or another engine type is done automatically depending on traffic and road conditions.

A third way to reduce the toxicity of exhaust gases is to install additional devices in the exhaust pipes, i.e. afterburners, which are toxin neutralizers equipped with expensive catalysts. An accessory increases the price of the car, reduces its power and economy, we did not achieve economy and environmental friendliness with the above two methods, so different types of wastewe have to use devices that reduce the toxicity of gases. In addition, one of the ways to ensure eco-efficiency is to increase the engine efficiency, reduce the tire vibration resistance, reduce the weight of the car using new materials, etc.

Summary

Currently, in order to improve the resource saving and environmental performance of cars, the cylinder deactivation method is being used in engine idle operation. The use of this method is especially good in cities, because in urban conditions there is a traffic light or a pedestrian crossing every 500-1000 meters, and the toxic gases released from it when the cars stop have a toxic effect on the surrounding enterprises and institutions. In this method, one or two cylinders are automatically turned off when the engine is idling at pedestrian crossings, traffic lights, and parking lots, while the other two cylinders provide the engine with idling power. The disadvantage of this method is that the cylinder deactivation algorithm has not been developed, so there are some flaws in which cylinders to deactivate and when.

Analysis of the problem of saving resources and ensuring environmental safety in the vehicle complex allows us to formulate a work goal, to achieve it, we perform the following tasks:

- Development of a method for improving the fuel-efficient and environmental performance of a modern car with an engine equipped with an electronic injection system;

- Development of a methodology for differentiated vehicle fuel consumption, taking into account the method of driving the engine in idle mode and operational conditions;

- development of a methodology for researching the effect of the proposed engine control method on the operational and standard fuel consumption of the car, the toxicity of the produced gases and vibration activity;

- development of a method of controlling the engine by turning off the cylinders of modern cars during operation;

- to study the influence of the rational algorithm of engine idle control on vibroacoustic, fuel-saving and environmental indicators in operational conditions.

As mentioned above, the amount of gases emitted by vehicles in urban conditions is very high, and this has a bad effect on the ecology and the health of city residents. To reduce this situation (harmful gases), it is necessary to avoid traffic jams in urban conditions and to reduce the use of private cars.

for this:

- the use of public transport should be convenient, high-quality and cheap;
- improvement of urban road infrastructure (road permeability).;
- it is necessary to improve intersections.

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